

Progress in surface curvature analysis of atomization through experiment

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Abstract

The curvature analysis of the flat fan spray is investigated in this study. The water and glycerol mixture was used as the working fluid. The Shadowgraph experiment was performed for the curvature analysis. The Shadowgraph images are processed with additional considerations when compared to the curvature studies of the previous experimental work. The evolution of the curvature along the spray direction was discussed. The direct droplet size distribution for the ligaments as well as complete droplets was given. The results show a good agreement between the ligaments and droplets. This study predicts the final spray distribution before primary atomization is complete. This approach has the potential to enhance the characterization of atomization and demonstrates the possible advantages of experimentally analyzing the complex interface morphology of the developing spray.

Keywords: Curvature distribution, Fan Spray, Primary breakup

1 Introduction

The atomization process of liquid sprays plays a major role in spray combustion inside industrial burners, turbojet engines, and rocket engines. The additional evaporation time scales involved in spray combustion typically enforce a fine and uniform droplet distribution. Fine droplet distribution is also required in the fields of medicine, powder metallurgy, painting, coating, and many other areas. The atomization process differs depending on the type of injector, the flow properties, and the conditions used. The measurement of droplet size distribution is essential for any type of application.

The previous studies have indicated that the downstream droplet distribution can be predicted using the curvature distribution of the surface at the initial stages of the spray. However, this approach has been tested in pressure swirl atomizers using different experimental and numerical techniques.

Vegad et al. [1] investigated the spray properties of a pressure swirl atomizer in the dense zone. The 2P-LIF technique was employed to circumvent the multiple scattering issue for imaging a plane in a dense spray. They effectively demonstrated the distribution of droplets by examining their morphology and validated their results using Phase Doppler Anemometry (PDA) measurements. Huang et al. [2] utilized the curvature-based method in the direct numerical simulation of a similar spray configuration, demonstrating excellent agreement with the experimental findings.

The droplet distribution through curvature analysis has been introduced by Canu et al. [3]. There are several ways through which the curvature distribution can be computed. A few notable methods are through the computation of the Hessian matrix [4], the triangulation method [5], and the divergence of the normal vector at the interface [6]. Among these techniques, the divergence of the normal vector at the interface is relatively simple and accurate. The usual steps in this method for analyzing curvature include finding the boundary between the liquid and gas, creating a smooth distance function across that boundary, and calculating curvature by looking at how the normal vector changes at the boundary. The curvature is then related to the droplet diameter. Since the fan spray is assumed to be two-dimensional, and the diameter and curvature are related as given in Eqn. 1.

$$D = \frac{2}{\kappa} \tag{1}$$

where κ is computed from the divergence of the normal gradient across the interface as given below.

$$\kappa = -\nabla \cdot \vec{n} \quad (2)$$

Furthermore the normal vector, \vec{n} , is computed using the distance function gradient across the interface and it is given in the following expression.

$$\vec{n} = \frac{\nabla \phi}{|\nabla \phi|} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ is the distance function which is defined positive inside the liquid volume and negative inside the air with zero level at the interface.

The droplet distribution is then weighted using the equivalent number of droplets. For this purpose, the length of the contour/perimeter should be measured at each location, each pixel, where the curvature is measured. The perimeter calculation involves Projected Phase Indicator (PPI) which is used to identify the projected liquid interface and the liquid surface. The PPI is defined in Eqn. 4.

$$PPI = 0.5 \times (1 + \tanh(\phi)) \quad (4)$$

The integration of the PPI field gives the total surface area covered by liquid in 2D and the integration of the gradient magnitude of the PPI field gives the perimeter. Therefore, the two-dimensional equivalent Sauter diameter can be written as given in Eqn. 5.

$$D_{21} = \frac{\int_s PPI ds}{\int_s |\nabla PPI| ds} \quad (5)$$

The previous work has applied the curvature analysis for the 2P-LIF images from a pressure swirl atomizer. Applying the same technique to the Shadowgraph images of a fan spray involves a few additional difficulties. One of the major issues is the high-intensity region inside the liquid sheet, at the interface, and inside the droplets. Another major issue is low spatial resolution, which affects interface detection and the smooth distance function across the interface. While interpolation can enhance the identification of a smooth interface, it is advisable to maintain a high spatial resolution.

The current study focuses on the curvature analysis of the primary atomization of the liquid sheet from the fan spray nozzle. This study also utilizes shadowgraph images for the computation of the curvature. The evaluation of the curvature along the liquid sheet and the prediction of droplet distribution even before the primary atomization will be demonstrated in this study.

Figure 1. Schematic of the experimental setup

Figure 2. Raw images obtained at (a) 0 mm and (b) 17 mm from the exit of the injector

2 Experimental methodology

For the analysis of the curvature distribution in the fan spray, the shadowgraph experiment is carried out. The schematic of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1. The flat fan spray nozzle (Lechler 8002E) with an exit hydraulic diameter of 1.1 mm and a semi-major axis of 1 mm was utilized to produce the fan spray. The water and glycerol mixture was used as the working fluid. The liquid mixture was kept at atmospheric conditions, and the pump-mounted mass flow controller was used to supply the liquid to the injector. A pulsed diode laser (Cavitar CAVILUX HF) was utilized as a light source, and the camera frame output was used for the synchronization. The high-speed CMOS camera (Phantom TMX 7510) was used for the imaging. A zoom lens with a focal length of 100 mm was utilized for good spatial resolution. The pixel and spatial resolutions were 1280×680 pixels² and 28.98 pixels/mm. The images were taken at 0 mm, and 20 mm from the exit of the injector. This was carried out to compute the evolution of curvature from the exit of the injector. The image processing was performed using a Python code that was developed in-house.

3 Results and discussion

The atomization process is typically divided into two phases: primary atomization and secondary atomization. Numerous events occur during the main atomization process. In fan sprays, the progression of droplets from the edges of the liquid sheet can be observed in multiple stages. Figure 2 displays the raw Shadowgraph images captured at distances of 0 mm and 17 mm from the injector exit. The liquid sheet remains mostly undisturbed close to the exit, with wave formation starting at the edges approximately 10 mm downstream from the injector exit. The small disturbances in the form of curved surfaces develop approximately 20 mm downstream of the exit due to the rapid inward movement of the liquid sheet caused by surface tension. The ligaments are seen approximately 30 mm from the exit. Subsequently, these ligaments detach from the rims and fragment into smaller droplets. The droplets emanating from the periphery of the liquid sheet can be anticipated from the initial phases, specifically up to 20 mm from the injector exit. The droplets generated from the central region of the spray exhibit a somewhat distinct pattern, which is also attributed to the interactions of surface waves. This explains the variation in droplet distribution in the lateral direction of the spray. Consequently, the present investigation is limited to the distribution of droplets emanating from the edges of the fan spray.

Figure 3 shows the merged raw image, Length-Curvature Distribution (LCD), and direct droplet size distribution (DSD) of the marked windows. More details about the processing steps involved in the curvature analysis are discussed later in this section (Fig. 5). The LCD is the curvature weighted based on the perimeter. The direct DSD is calculated based on the curvature as given by the Eqn. 1 and the resultant diameter is weighted based on the equivalent number of droplets given by the perimeter. The droplets with only with the positive curvatures are taken with the maximum value fixed based on the distribution itself. The This distribution was obtained for 100 images and the average distribution is plotted. The LCD was narrow close to the injector where the surface waves were not yet developed. For the W2 window, the LCD became broader than it was for the W1 window due to the evolution of surface waves. Moreover, the distribution was symmetric for both W1, and W2 windows. The LCD distribution for the W3 window further broadened; however, it was asymmetrical with a larger distribution towards the positive curvature side. Further downstream inside the W4 window, the LCD became more positive than it was for the W3 window. This distribution would eventually become completely positive when the droplets were detached from the liquid sheet. The direct DSD shows very large values for the window W1 as expected. As the curvature evolve along the spray direction, the distribution becomes narrower

Figure 3. (a) The merged raw image, (b) length-curvature distribution, and (c) direct droplet size distribution of the marked windows

Figure 4. The Shadowgraph image obtained at 20 mm from the injector exit

and start to converged to the final DSD.

The raw image shown in Fig. 4 is obtained at 20 mm from the injector exit. This image was used for the curvature analysis because the image contains a few stages in the final evolution of droplets from the rims. The three marked regions are selected for the comparison of droplet distribution before and after the droplet formation. The window A contains only the attached ligaments, and window B includes attached and detached ligaments with a large window, and window C contains mostly droplets.

Figure 5. Different processing steps involved in the curvature analysis

The processing steps involved in the curvature analysis is shown in Fig. 5 for window B. The processing steps involve denoising of the actual Shadowgraph images and the sub-pixel interpolation for capturing very fine curvatures. The image is then binarized to distinguish the liquid and air interface. The interface contour is then extracted for the computation of the distance function. The curvature is finally calculated using the distance function as discussed earlier.

Figure 6 illustrates LCD and direct DSD derived from curvature analysis for windows A, B, and C. A total of 200 images were utilized for the computation to enhance the statistics. The curvature for windows A and B exhibits a nearly identical distribution on the negative curvature side, with only a minor variation observed on the positive curvature side. In the context of positive curvature, window B exhibits elevated values in high-curvature regions and diminished values in low-curvature regions, relative to window A. Window C, predominantly containing droplets, exhibits a positive curvature distribution. The droplet distribution from windows A and B exhibits a minor discrepancy. This results from the supplementary processes that take place downstream of window A. The processes involve the interaction of surface waves with the rims and the interaction among the ligaments. These processes result in the generation of minor disturbances, subsequently leading to the formation of small droplets. Window C exhibits marginally elevated distributions for smaller droplets than Window B. The variation in direct DSD between windows B and C could be due to the following reason. The fine droplets likely enter this window from the central region of the spray because of the significant horizontal velocities. The formation of droplets from the central region of the sheet differs from the detachment of droplets from the edges of the liquid sheet. The interaction of surface waves generates fine droplets in the central region of the liquid sheet. This study was focused only on the analysis of the droplets generated from the edges of the liquid sheet. The curvature analysis is also applicable to the central region of the spray; however, the presence of fine droplets and wave structures requires high resolution and a modified processing approach. This curvature analysis effectively predicts the final droplet distribution prior to primary atomization.

The D_{21} marked in the droplet distribution also show change throughout windows A, B, and C. For the calculation of D_{21} , only the rims are considered for windows A and B. If the whole liquid sheet is considered the surface area would be very large and this would yield a very large D_{21} . However, the whole liquid sheet is not contributing to the formation of the droplets from the rims of the liquid sheet. The difference in the D_{21} among windows is about 45% and this could be reduced by only considering the ligaments for the surface calculation.

Figure 6. (a) Length curvature distribution, and (b) direct droplet size distribution from windows A, B, and C

Conclusions

The curvature analysis was carried out for the flat fan spray. The experimental Shadowgraph images were used for the analysis. The process of droplet formation was shown through the evolution of the curvature along the axial direction using four different windows. The process of droplet formation involves the initial flat edges followed by symmetric disturbances with small curvatures. The disturbances grow along the axial direction, and the curvature distribution becomes asymmetrical. The curvature distribution skews towards the positive side and completely becomes positive at the end of the formation of droplets. The comparison of direct DSD was given for the ligaments as well as pure droplets. In this atomization system we notice first a certain convergence of LCD for high positive value and direct DSD. This zone correspond to the atomization of the side rim producing a certain class of droplet. Eventually atomization starts at the tip of the liquid sheet due to different phenomena such as liquid sheet flapping with respect to side rim atomization. The surface curvature analysis allows for detecting this effect and to see the establishment of the final DSD, but additional measurement downstream of the liquid sheet tip are necessary to complete the observation of this phenomena and the probable bimodal DSD.

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